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O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLINING DINAMIK O'SISHI TAHLILI

ANALYSIS OF DYNAMIC POPULATION GROWTH IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

АНАЛИЗ ДИНАМИКИ РОСТА НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН

ANNOTATSIIYA

Demografiya aholining o'sishi va har bir ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy tizimning rivojlanish qonuniyatlarini alohida o'rganadi, chunki har bir ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy shakllanishga xos bo'lgan aholining o'sish qonuni demografik vaziyatga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Demografik jarayonlarni o'rganishda katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlar qo'llaniladi. Ko'pgina mamlakatlarda demografik ma'lumotlar statistik tashkilotlar tomonidan to'planadi. Ular aholining soni, tarkibi va demografik jarayonlarini aks ettiradi va ushbu masalalar bo'yicha raqamli jadvallar va diagramma ma'lumotlarini, ilmiy manbalarni va sotsiologik-demografik tadqiqotlar natijalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu maqolada so'nggi yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasi aholisining dinamik o'sishi, demografik rivojlanish tarixi, aholining joylashishi va zichligi, mamlakatda tabiiy ko'payish jarayoni, aholi migratsiyasi va urbanizatsiya darajasi, mamlakat aholisining milliy tuzilishi tahlil qilinadi.

ANNOTATION

Demography studies the laws of population growth and development of each socio-economic system separately, because the law of population growth specific to each socio-economic formation has a direct impact on the demographic situation. A large amount of data is used in the study of demographic processes. In most countries, demographic data are collected by statistical organizations. They reflect the number, composition and demographic processes of the population, and include numerical tables and diagrammatic data on these issues, scientific sources, and the results of sociological-demographic research. This article analyzes the dynamic growth of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, the history of demographic development, the location and density of the population, the process of natural reproduction in the country, the level of population migration and urbanization, and the national structure of the country's population.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Демография изучает закономерности роста населения и развития каждой социально-экономической системы в отдельности, поскольку закономерности роста населения, характерные для каждой социально-экономической формации, оказывают непосредственное влияние на демографическую ситуацию. При изучении демографических процессов используется большой объем данных. В большинстве стран демографические данные собираются статистическими организациями. Они отражают численность, состав и демографические процессы населения и включают цифровые таблицы и схематические данные по этим вопросам, научные источники и результаты социолого-демографических исследований. В данной статье анализируется динамичный рост численности населения Республики Узбекистан за последние годы, история демографического развития, размещение и плотность населения, процесс естественного воспроизводства в стране, уровень миграции населения и урбанизации, а также национальная структура населения страны.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

demografiya, aholining o'sishi, demografik rivojlanish, dinamik o'sish, aholi zichligi, tabiiy ko'payish jarayoni, aholi migratsiyasi darajasi, urbanizatsiya.

KEYWORDS

demography, population growth, demographic development, dynamic growth, density of population, process of natural reproduction, level of population migration, urbanization.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

демография, прирост населения, демографическое развитие, динамичный рост, плотность населения, процесс естественного воспроизводства, уровень миграции населения, урбанизация.

Demographics of Uzbekistan are demographic indicators of the population of Uzbekistan, including population growth, density, nationality, education level, health, economic status, religious affiliation and other aspects.

The socio-economic and demographic development of the population of Uzbekistan has changed dramatically since the second half of the 19th century after the occupation by Tsarist Russia. This situation was reflected in the number of the population, national and age-sex composition, growth rates, location features. Peasants were moved from Russia and settled in Mirzachol, Uyghurs were moved from Eastern Turkestan and a place was allocated for them in the mountain valleys in the east of the republic. According to the population census conducted in 1897, there were 3.9 million people in the territory of Uzbekistan. people lived, of which 19% were urban residents. Migration mobility of indigenous population was low. Population growth at the expense of immigrants was the result of the colonial policy of the tsarist government. Thanks to this policy, new villages and towns were built in the country. However, between 1865 and 1900, the population increased by 0.6%. Even in the first quarter of the 20th century, there was no significant change in population growth. During the years 1924-40, the population of Uzbekistan was 2.3 million. per person, population growth equaled 3% per year.

The Second World War had a very negative impact on the population of Uzbekistan, its structure and location. As a result of the war, the republic lost more than 1 million inhabitants. The total population in 1940-45 was 6.6 million. 5.2 million per person. decreased to a person.

In the post-war period, there were positive changes in population growth rates. The population increased from 5.2 million to 8.4 million. In this case too, the weight of the population transferred from abroad was greater than the pure natural increase. In the 60-80s of the 20th century, the number of Uzbeks in the population of the republic increased regularly at a high rate. In 1989, Uzbeks made up 71.4% of the republic's population.

The transition of Uzbekistan to the path of independent development necessitated the transition to a new stage in its demographic history. As a result of the formation of market relations, changes in socio-economic and political conditions in the republic, a new demographic process began: the birth rate decreased sharply, the country's Slavic peoples, Jews, Meskhetian Turks, Greeks, Ukrainians, Germans, etc. a certain part of peoples their historical lands, etc. moved to foreign countries. The largest negative migration balance was observed in 1990 and amounted to 181,200 people. These demographic processes led to a decrease in the growth rate of the population of Uzbekistan. During the next 15 years, the population of the republic increased by 4.8 million, the growth rate was 1.8%, the average annual absolute increase was 400 thousand people. The population of the republic is concentrated in oases and valleys, which have been developed since ancient times, and the conditions are favorable for irrigated agriculture.

Cities and towns that were created as a result of the development of Mirzachol, Surkhan-Sherabad, Karshi, Central Fergana, Ellikkala deserts and on the basis of the discovery of deposits of various mineral resources also made changes in the territorial structure of the population. However, the new settlements could not make significant changes to the territorial forms of the population that have been formed over the centuries. The main part of the population lives in the place where they were born and raised. The population living in desert regions is excluded from this. At the same time, changes in the network of cities had a great impact on the dynamics and location of the city's population. In the following years, significant changes took place in them. In 1990-2005, when the country's population growth rate was decreasing, this process was slower in some regions.

The most important features of the demographic situation in Uzbekistan are the decreasing population growth rates; decrease in the rate of natural population increase; negative effects of external migration; slow growth of urban

population and others. The country's urban population is extremely unevenly distributed, and the main part of it is in the city of Tashkent. However, Tashkent sh. its population has hardly grown in recent years, as a result of which its share in the population of Uzbekistan fell from 10.5% to 8.2% in 2020. The demographic potential of Navoi, Syrdarya, Tashkent regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan has decreased. Currently, 16.4% of the population of Uzbekistan belongs to Samarkand and Jizzakh regions. There was also a slight increase in Khorezm, Namangan and Andijan regions.

In 1991-2005, a significant disparity was observed in the growth of the urban population in the regions of Uzbekistan. In these years, the growth rate of the population of the republic's cities is 0.9%, this indicator is 3.2% in Samarkand; 2.8% in Jizzakh; 0.6% in Syrdarya; 0.7% in Bukhara; It was 0.8% in Khorezm and 0.2% in Tashkent region.

Despite the above changes, the level of territorial integration of the population of the republic is still high in Fergana and Tashkent economic regions. 28% of the country's population went to the Fergana Valley, Tashkent region. and 18% corresponds to the region. The population density is 58 people per 1 km², which varies 70 times nationally, or in other words, it ranges from 7.3 people (Navoi region) to 552.5 (Andijan region). Fergana, Namangan, Khorezm regions are densely populated, Kashkadarya, Syrdarya, Bukhara regions, as well as the Republic of Karakalpakstan, have a much lower population density.

36.3% of the total population of the Republic of Uzbekistan lives in cities, and the rest in villages. In recent years, there has been a decrease in the level of urbanization and an increase in the share of the rural population.

Population density of Uzbekistan by municipalities

Figure 1. Density of the population of Uzbekistan by municipality, according to population estimates in 2020.

More detailed information on natural population growth in Uzbekistan is available from the second half of the 19th century. Natural population increase depends on the number 1 birth

rate. The birth rate was high in the republic at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. In 1865-1917, the total birth rate (number of births per 1000 people) was 4550%.

Childbirth was at the level of physiological possibility, the birth of children in the family was not limited. The main factors of this are the social status of Uzbek women. low level of education, relatively high influence of traditions and values supporting childbirth, and high infant mortality.

During that period, the number of deaths among the population was also high. In the years 1886-1900, on the territory of Uzbekistan, an average of 49.8 children were born per 1000 inhabitants, while the number of deaths (per 1000 people) was equal to 44.8. Therefore, despite the high birth rate in Uzbek families at that time, the natural increase of the population was slow due to the large number of deaths among the population and the fact that the average life expectancy was very short (32 years). In other words, a high birth rate could not ensure a high natural increase, the level of "utility" of birth was low. These evidences show that the natural increase of the population of Uzbekistan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century was 3.5 times less than that of European nations. As a result, population growth has been very slow. In 1885-1917, the population of Uzbekistan increased from 3,320,000 to 4,052,000, or the population grew by an average of 0.6% annually. This indicator is 3.1 times less than now, because in 1991-2000, the population of Uzbekistan increased by 1.9% per year.

During 1939-2004, i.e. during 65 years, the population of the republic increased by 4.0 times, while this indicator was 6.4 times in urban areas and 3.3 times in rural areas. Of course, the growth rate of the population was different in different intervals of the considered period and in rural and urban areas. In particular, in 1939-1959, the total population grew by 127.9%, the urban population by 185.6%, and the rural population by 108.5%. In 1959-1970, the total population of the republic increased by 145.3%, urban population by 158.4%, and rural population by 141.3%, the average annual increase was 3.45%, 4.25%, and 3.20%. It was during these years that Uzbekistan reached the highest indicators of its historical demographic development.

In the following years, the growth of the population slowed down a bit, but the process of increasing the urban population faster than the rural population remained. For example, in 1970-1979, the urban population increased by 146.9%, the rural population by 120.9%, and the total population by 130.4%. During 1979-1989, the urban population grew by 126.7% and the rural population by 130.1%. It can be seen that the demographic development of rural areas of the republic was better than that of cities and towns from this period. Such a weakening of the urbanization process began in the second half of the 80s of the last century, in 1984 the share of the urban population rose to 42%, and after that it gradually decreased.

In recent years, the rate of increase of the total population of the republic has decreased and the rural population is growing faster than the urban population. At the moment, the growth rate of the city's population has fallen to the lowest level (1.05%). In 2000-05, the average population growth rate was 1.2%, and the average annual absolute population growth was 310,400 people. During this period, the rural population increased by 4.4 million, and the urban population by 1 million. As a result, the share of urban population dropped from 40.4% to 35.9%.

According to the coefficients of birth and natural reproduction, the rural population of the republic's regions can be proportionally divided into 2 groups: the first includes 8 regions with an average birth rate (20-22%) and natural reproduction rate (14-17%) (Bukhara, Andijan, Navoi, Namangan, Syrdarya, Fergana, Khorezm, Tashkent).

The second group with a relatively high birth rate (23-24%) and natural reproduction rate (18-19%) includes Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Samarkand regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The average birth rate (16.20%) among urban residents is observed in 8 regions. In Namangan region, the birth rate of urban residents is relatively high (20.2%). There are 4 provinces with a low birth rate (16%) among the urban

population. These are Bukhara, Tashkent, Samarkand and Fergana regions.

In 1991, as a result of the formation of new economic relations, socio-economic changes took place in Uzbekistan, and these changes firstly affected its demographic situation. One of the main reasons for the relatively high birth rate in Uzbekistan is family values and the high rate of marriage. For example, in 2005, there were 7.0 marriages per 1,000 people in urban areas, while the divorce rate was 0.6. In 1991-2004, the number of children born in Uzbekistan per 1,000 inhabitants decreased from 34.5 to 22.3 or by 1.2 points. In 2005, the population increased by 292.1 thousand people or by 1.1% compared to 2004.

The fertility rate in Uzbekistan is also decreasing. The majority of children are born to relatively young women. This situation has become more stable in recent years. In 1980-1995, the death rate in the republic decreased from 7.5 per thousand to 6.4 per thousand. This process is mainly due to the reduction of mortality among infants, children and middle-aged people. The development of medical services to the population led to a sharp decrease in the number of deaths of the population. If in 1886-1920 the number of deaths per 1,000 people in Uzbekistan was 4,034, after 1920 this figure decreased by 56 times. Population mortality is higher in urban areas of the republic compared to rural areas. The reason for this is changes in the ecological situation, urban lifestyle. The population death rate is highest in the industrially developed Tashkent region. The number of deaths in 2005 compared to 2004 increased by 6.6% or 8.6 thousand people. The infant mortality rate decreased from 15.4% in 2004 to 14.3%.

Migration in Uzbekistan also has its own characteristics. In the 60s and 70s of the last century, in connection with the development of Mirzachol, a certain part of the population moved here from the Fergana Valley and some districts of Samarkand and Jizzakh regions. Internal migration of the population was also connected with the development of Karshi, Surkhan-Sherobod steppes. The population of Syrdarya, Jizzakh,

Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions and the newly established rural districts in the Fergana Valley was mainly formed as a result of migration.

In the following years, there is a decrease in internal migration movements in Uzbekistan. One of the main reasons for this is the process of complex socio-economic changes in the conditions of transition to a market economy. The level of employment of the population is directly affected by internal migration flows in the country. In 1980-2003, the internal migration of the republic increased from 461,800 to 250,000 people, the migration within the regions also increased from 253,600 to 138,000, i.e. 118,600 people, and the inter-regional migration from 208,200 to 115,000 people, i.e. decreased by 93.2 thousand people.

In the 1990s, due to the deterioration of the ecological situation in the archipelago, the migration of people from some districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan to Tashkent and Syrdarya regions was observed.

Urbanization is determined not only by the total number of cities and towns, but also by the development of more urban agglomerations. According to the data of 2005, there are 17 large cities in Uzbekistan. The city of Tashkent stands out among them. The influence of the capital city with a population of more than 2,995 thousand on the process of urbanization in the republic is enormous. In this way, the process of urbanization in Uzbekistan is taking place depending on the city of Tashkent, large and medium-sized cities. On the basis of large cities, a complex territorial system of cities, urban agglomerations have emerged, which serve as an important indicator of the development of urbanization. For example, Tashkent agglomeration unites about 30 cities and towns. Also, Fergana, Margilon, Samarkand, Namangan, Bukhara, Andijan, etc. agglomerations are also developing.

The total rate of urbanization in Uzbekistan was more than 42% in 1984. In the future, the scale of urbanization is also affected by the decrease in the natural growth rate of the city's population.

The decrease in the level of urbanization was caused by the faster increase of the rural population compared to the urban population, the increase of external migration in cities (especially in industrial centers), and the lack of creation of new cities. However, socio-economic reforms in rural areas, establishment of infrastructure and industrial enterprises, recreation centers, development of entrepreneurship in non-agricultural economic sectors represent the real state of urbanization. Based on these changes and the development of cities, the overall rate of urbanization in Uzbekistan will stop decreasing and begin to increase in the coming years.

The socio-economic and political environment of Uzbekistan, in particular, the fact that it has been a colony for almost 150 years, had a great impact on its demographic development, including the national composition of the population. About the population, that is, the total number of the population, regional distribution, age, sex, social and national structure, natural growth, migration, etc. complete information is obtained by conducting a population census. In the next 100 years, the population census in Uzbekistan was conducted several times (in 1897, 1920, 1926, 1939, 1959, 1970, 1979 and 1989).

Uzbekistan is one of the multinational republics of the world. Comparing the data of previous years, according to the 1939 census, 97, 113 according to the 1959 census, and more than 120 nationalities and ethnic groups lived in the 1979 census. According to the 1989 census, representatives of more than 125 nationalities and peoples live in Uzbekistan, their total number is 19 million. It turned out that there are 810 thousand people.

The indigenous people of Uzbekistan are Uzbeks. In recent years, the share of Uzbeks in the national structure of the population has increased and now 80.0% of the population of the republic. Karakalpaks are the second indigenous people in the republic. Their total number is 549.2 thousand people or 2.2% of the country's population. Tajiks (1237.4 thousand or 4.9%), Kazakhs (977.8 thousand 3.6%), Kyrgyz (227.4 thousand 0.9%),

Turkmens (152.3 thousand 0) from the local peoples of Central Asia in the Republic of Uzbekistan (0.6%) also live. The number of Tatars living in Uzbekistan is quite large (275.4 thousand people, 1.0%).

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, Poles, Czechs, Bulgarians, etc. also lives. According to the 1989 population census, Russians were in second place in terms of number. and is in 3rd place, more than 1050 thousand people or 3.8% of the total population. If we look at the dynamics of the number of Russians living in Uzbekistan, the fastest increase occurs in the 1959-70s. The reason for this is the reconstruction of the city after the 1966 Tashkent earthquake and the establishment of new industrial centers in the republic, which attracted many Russian and European peoples. However, in the following years, the growth rate of Russians decreased somewhat.

Besides the Tajiks, who belong to the Indo-European family, there are also Persian, Pashtun, Baluch and other peoples in Uzbekistan. Koreans, Armenians and Jews also live in the country.

The geographical location of nationalities in the country is also uneven. The first reason for this is the historical development of nations, and the second is the characteristics of the development of national economic sectors in the republic. In rural areas, the number of representatives of indigenous peoples is increasing, and the number of representatives of other nationalities is decreasing. Karakalpaks are a nation that fully lives within its own republic (94.5%). During the period of independent development of the Uzbek people, a great change took place in the national composition of the population. Currently, the number of Uzbeks in Uzbekistan has increased by 8.6% compared to 1989.

The number of permanent residents in Uzbekistan is increasing by an average of 2.1 thousand people every day. As of January 1, 2023, the permanent population of Uzbekistan was 36,024,946 people.

According to the Statistics Agency under the President of Uzbekistan, the population of the

country increased by 753,600 people in 2022. In 2022, the population of Uzbekistan increased by an average of 62,800 people per month. It is said that the number of permanent residents increased by 2.1 thousand people on average every day of 2022. For information, the Republic of Uzbekistan ranks third in the CIS in terms of permanent population.

In addition, Uzbekistan ranks first in the CIS in terms of birth rate. The Republic of Uzbekistan ranks 41st among the countries of the world in terms of population.

As of July 1, 2023, the total number of permanent residents of the republic amounted to 36,372,300 people, an increase of 2.2% compared to the corresponding period of 2022. The Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan shared information about this.

According to this information, 18,066.0 of the population are women and 18,306.3 are men. 18,557.5 thousand of them live in urban areas, and 17,815.8 thousand live in rural areas.

Figure 2. Permanent population by region (as of July 1, 2023).

The population of Uzbekistan is 36.4 million people, most of them live in Samarkand. Statistics Agency reported that as of July 1, the permanent population of Uzbekistan is 36.4 million people. The largest population lives in Samarkand (4 million 159 thousand), and the least in Syrdarya (904.9 thousand). The Statistics Agency provided information on the demographic indicators of Uzbekistan as of July 1, 2023. The population is 36.4 million people (in 2021 this number was 34.9 million, in 2022 it was 35.6

million people). 18.1 million of them are women, and 18.3 million are men. 18.6 million people live in cities, while 17.8 million people live in rural areas.

The number of births in the first 6 months of the year was 434,500. The most populated area in Uzbekistan is Samarkand region (4 million 159 thousand people).

The following regions are Fergana (4 million 14 thousand people), Kashkadarya (3 million 515 thousand people), Andijan (3 million 354 thousand people) and Namangan (3 million 28

thousand people). There are 3 million 19 thousand permanent residents in Tashkent region, 2 million 999 thousand in Tashkent city, 2 million 836 thousand in Surkhandarya, and 2 million 24 thousand in Bukhara.

The region with the least number of Uzbeks is the Syrdarya region, where 904,900 people live. The following places were occupied by Navoi (1 million 65 thousand people), Jizzakh (1 million 491 thousand people), Khorezm (1 million 971 thousand people) and Karakalpakstan (1 million 987 thousand people).

The most densely populated region is the city of Tashkent - 6,695.4 people per 1 square kilometer. This figure is 780 in Andijan, 593.9 in Fergana, and 407 in Namangan. At the same time, this figure is 11.9 in Karakalpakstan, and 9.6 in Navoi.

Regarding the number of marriages, 98,700 cases were recorded, and the number of divorces was 25,400. In 7 months, 1,600 people immigrated to the country, and 9,000 people emigrated.

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